

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OBSERVED IN THE COURSE OF SCLEROTIC HYPERTROPHY OF ADENOIDS IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The sclerotic hypertrophic form of adenoids is mainly observed in older children and adolescents with chronic adenoiditis. In this condition, pronounced proliferation of connective tissue is detected, originating from the base of the pharyngeal lymphoid tissue adjacent to the palatine bone and extending toward the periosteum. The connective tissue bundles are characterized by a low cellular content and coarse fibrous structure, forming thick strands that extend from the basal layer of the adenoid tissue to its superficial layers.

Relevance of the problem

According to data from leading clinical centers worldwide, diseases of the lymphoid pharyngeal ring (Waldeyer's lymphadenoid ring) occupy a leading position among otorhinolaryngological pathologies in childhood. The proportion of children with chronic adenoid tonsillitis ranges from 20% to 50%, while among frequently ill children it reaches 37–70% (H.M. Makkaev, 2002; Yu.V. Mishunin et al., 2003; V.P. Bikova, D.V. Kalinin, 2011; A.I. Nikolaeva, 2011; M. Gouletal, 2007).

The highest prevalence of lymphadenoid pharyngeal ring pathology is observed in children aged 3 to 7 years, regardless of place of residence. However, pathology of the pharyngeal tonsil is significantly more common (2.1 times) in children living in areas with high levels of air pollution compared to those residing in environmentally favorable regions.

Under normal physiological conditions, the nasopharyngeal tonsil, like other tonsils of the Pirogov–Waldeyer ring, plays an essential role in maintaining immune homeostasis and ensuring full induction of antigen-specific adaptive immune responses (M.Z. Saidov et al., 2011). The causes of hypertrophy of the pharyngeal tonsil include childhood infectious diseases (measles, whooping cough, scarlet fever, diphtheria, influenza, etc.), as well as acute and chronic inflammatory diseases of the upper respiratory tract. At the same time, constitutional characteristics of the child also play a significant role. This is supported by cases in which hypertrophy of the pharyngeal lymphoid apparatus occurs without an evident inflammatory component. Such conditions are regarded in pediatrics as manifestations of constitutional anomalies, namely lymphatic-hypoplastic diathesis, which may lead to the development of *status thymicolymphaticus*, secondary immunodeficiency, and difficulties in treatment.

Materials and methods

Morphological and immunohistochemical studies of nasopharyngeal tonsils were performed in 64 children aged 1 to 10 years diagnosed with adenoid disease and treated at the ADTI Clinic and the private IMPULS Clinic during the period from 2020 to 2024. The study evaluated age-related prevalence and pathomorphological features of adenoids using clinical-anamnestic, morphological, and statistical research methods.

Discussion and results

The sclerotic hypertrophic form of adenoids is predominantly observed in older children and adolescents with chronic adenoiditis. In this form, marked proliferation of connective tissue is noted at the base of the pharyngeal lymphoid tissue, beginning from the area adjacent to the palatine bone and extending toward the periosteum. The connective tissue bundles exhibit a coarse fibrous structure with low cellularity and are distributed as thick strands extending from the basal layers of the adenoid tissue to its superficial layers.

Between the connective tissue bundles, inflammatory infiltrates and clusters of lymphoid cells are identified. On the opposite side of the connective tissue strands, tissue bundles composed of reticular and fibrocytic cells are observed. Perinodular cells form characteristic clusters, which are arranged in a manner suggestive of future nodule formation. Within these nodules and surrounding cellular aggregates, chronic inflammatory cells predominate.

To determine the predominance of collagen fibers in the sclerotic and fibromatous forms of adenoids, Van Gieson's picrofuchsin staining was applied. This method revealed collagen fibers arranged as large bundles oriented in various directions: circularly around blood vessels and irregularly in other areas. Examination under high magnification demonstrated that individual small collagen bundles are arranged parallel to each other, forming curved and tortuous patterns.

Conclusion

In the sclerotic hypertrophic form of adenoids, large fibrous bundles are observed in the basal part of the lymphoid tissue, while smaller bundles predominate in the apical region. The fibers are coarse, and the cellular composition is dominated by lymphohistiocytic cells characteristic of chronic inflammatory processes. The tissue architecture is predominantly disorganized, and in some cases, nodule formation is observed.

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